

Study of Association of Strontium Nitrate in Glycerol-H₂O Mixtures at different Temperatures using Conductometric Technique

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The association constants for Sr(NO₃)₂ have been determined in 10, 30 and 50% glycerol-H₂O mixtures at 25, 30, 35 and 40° using conductometric technique. The data have been analysed by the Fuoss and Edelson method. Only the constants for the ion-pair of SrNO₃⁺ (K_A) have been studied. K_A tends to increase in the order: 10% < 30% < 50% glycerol-H₂O, while it decreases with temperature. Thermodynamic parameters ΔH°, ΔG° and ΔS° for the ion-pair formation are obtained and discussed. Also, Walden products (Λ₀η) are reported. The effect of solvent on the association processes of SrNO₃⁺ is discussed in terms of cation and anion solvations.

The formation of ion-pairs and complexes in solutions of electrolytes is a subject which has undergone considerable development during the past 50 years. Many works had been done on the association of 1 : 1, 2 : 1 and 2 : 2 electrolytes in aqueous¹ and mixed solvents media^{2,3}. Perchlorate and nitrate salts have great ability to dissociate into ions in aqueous media and for this reason they are used as ionic fixer. In mixed and non-aqueous solvents these salts exhibit ionic association to some extent. In a previous communication⁴, we presented data on the association of Ba(NO₃)₂ in glycol-H₂O, mixtures at 25° using conductance measurements.

Here we present the results of the association of Sr(NO₃)₂ in 10, 30 and 50% glycerol-H₂O mixtures, determined at different temperatures using conductometric technique. The thermodynamic parameters are also evaluated.

Mathematical model :

The conductometric data have been treated by the Fuoss and Edelson method⁵. In our solutions, the following ionic equilibria are considered :

It is generally thought that K_{1A} >> K_{2A}. Therefore, they established a theory on the assumption that K_{1A} >> K_{2A} and proposed the following equation (K_{1A} can be replaced by K_A) :

$$\Delta F = \Lambda_0 - XK_A/\Lambda_0 \quad (3)$$

where,

$$X = c f_{+2} \Lambda F (\Lambda F - \Lambda_0/2) \quad (4)$$

$$F = \frac{[(1 - \delta c^{1/2})^{-1} + (\Lambda_0 - \lambda_0)/2\Lambda]}{[1 + (\Lambda_0 - \lambda_0)/2\Lambda_0]} \quad (5)$$

where, Λ and Λ₀ are the equivalent and the limiting equivalent conductances respectively, λ₀ is the limiting equivalent conductance of NO₃⁻, δ the Onsager's slope, divided by Λ₀, and c the molar concentration of NO₃⁻. The ion activity coefficient of Sr²⁺ (f₂₊) was estimated by the Debye-Hückel second approximation,

$$\log f_{2+} = -A Z_1^2 I^{1/2} / (1 + B a I^{1/2}) \quad (6)$$

where, A and B are Debye-Hückel constants, I is the ionic strength of the solution, Z₁ the valency of metal ion Sr²⁺, and a the ion size parameter (a = 5 Å, for Sr²⁺).

Since, however, there is no available data of the λ₀ values in glycerol-H₂O mixtures at different temperatures, we have calculated λ₀ at any temperature by multiplying the ratio of value of Λ₀ at that temperature to that at 25° by λ₀ value at 25°. The above procedure is then iterated until λ₀ becomes a constant value. It is not then necessary that λ₀ be determined very accurately, partly because K_A's that can be evaluated involve relatively large error and partly because λ₀ does not control the values of K_A and Λ₀ strongly. Fig. 1 shows the plots according to equation 3 for Sr(NO₃)₂ in 10, 30 and 50% glycerol-H₂O mixtures at 25°. The results from such plots are summarised in Table 2.

It is clearly desirable to obtain the standard enthalpy change (ΔH°) by studying the association constant (K_A) over a range of temperature by means of van't Hoff's isochore, where log K_A values are plotted against 1/T, giving a straight line with slope -ΔH°/R. The standard Gibbs energy changes (ΔG°) can be calculated from equation,

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_A \quad (7)$$

Also, the standard entropy change (ΔS°) can be evaluated from equation (8),

$$\Delta S^\circ = (\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ)/T \quad (8)$$

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Fig. 1. ΔF against X for $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ at 25° . (●) 10%, (○) 30% and (●) 50% glycerol-H₂O mixtures

Results and Discussion

Density⁶, viscosity⁶ and dielectric constant⁷ data of glycerol-water mixtures at different temperatures taken from literature are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF DENSITY, VISCOSITY AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF GLYCEROL-H₂O MIXTURES AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Glycerol %	Property	25°	30°	35°	40°
10	Density (g cm ⁻³)	1.020	1.014	1.007	1.001
	Viscosity (cP)	1.153	1.024	0.911	0.790
	Dielectric constant	75.70	73.88	72.19	70.41
30	Density (g cm ⁻³)	1.070	1.063	1.057	1.050
	Viscosity (cP)	2.157	1.876	1.637	1.407
	Dielectric constant	70.00	68.23	66.53	64.87
50	Density (g cm ⁻³)	1.123	1.116	1.109	1.102
	Viscosity (cP)	5.041	4.247	3.591	2.951
	Dielectric constant	64.00	62.28	60.87	59.55

TABLE 2—VALUES OF LIMITING EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCES (Λ_0) AND ASSOCIATION CONSTANT (K_A) OF $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ IN GLYCEROL-H₂O MIXTURES AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Glycerol %	t_0 C	Λ_0 cm ² Ω ⁻¹	K_A dm ³ mol ⁻¹
10	25	198.04	8.79
	30	218.98	7.52
	35	239.08	6.44
	40	259.38	5.35
30	25	125.45	14.18
	30	139.00	12.51
	35	152.47	10.91
	40	166.49	9.60
50	25	57.78	25.04
	30	63.80	23.20
	35	70.12	21.14
	40	76.50	18.36

Inspection of the data of Table 2 shows that the values of Λ_0 of $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ decrease as the proportion of glycerol in the mixture increases. But as the temperature increases, the Λ_0 values increase for all glycerol-H₂O mixtures. The trends in Λ_0 's can be discussed through another characteristic function called Walden product, $\Lambda_0\eta$. Although, the Λ_0 value decreases as the proportion of glycerol increases, however, the $\Lambda_0\eta$ value (Table 3) increases due to the increase of the viscosity (η) value. The $\Lambda_0\eta$ values decrease with an increase in temperature at 25–40° for all glycerol-H₂O mixtures. The decrease in $\Lambda_0\eta$ is small. The behaviour of the Walden products can be summarised by the function,

$$d(\Lambda_0\eta)/dT = 0.5 d\Lambda_0/dT \quad (9)$$

The decrease in $\Lambda_0\eta$ with temperature, which is often in aqueous solutions⁸, can probably be interpreted as a thermal expansion of the solvent sheath (which envelops an ion and moves with it by ion-solvent interaction), i.e. the expansion of a solvated ion, because of the activation of solvent molecules forming the sheath.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF ACTIVATION ENERGY (E) AND WALDEN PRODUCTS ($\Lambda_0\eta$) OF $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ IN GLYCEROL-H₂O MIXTURES AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Glycerol %	E kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Lambda_0\eta$			
		25°	30°	35°	40°
10	14.18	228.34	224.24	217.80	204.91
30	14.73	270.60	260.76	249.59	234.25
50	15.19	291.27	270.96	251.80	225.75

There are very marked characteristics in the K_A values. The K_A generally decreases as the temperature is increased; the thermal motion probably destroys the solvent structure. However, K_A value increases as the proportion of glycerol increases in the mixture.

Since the conductance of an ion depends on rate of movement, it seems reasonable to treat conductance in a manner analogous to that employed for other processes

taking place at a definite rate which increases with temperature. On this basis it would be possible to write,

$$\Lambda_0 = A e^{-E/RT} \quad (10)$$

where, A is a constant, E the activation energy of the process, and R the general constant of gases. The values of E derived in the present work are listed in Table 3. It is obvious that E value increases as the proportion of glycerol increases in the mixture. It is well accepted that the activation energy for electrolytic conductance is almost identical with that for the viscous flow of the solvent; the consistency of E means that the positive temperature coefficient of ion conductance is roughly equal to the negative temperature coefficient of viscosity⁹.

If we consider that from a rudimentary standpoint the ion-pair is formed with only the action of the coulombic force in a continuum medium, both the values of ΔH° and ΔS° of the ion-pair formation will be negative. Therefore, all the experimental values of ΔH° and ΔS° are negative (Table 4). The negative sign of ΔH° means that the association processes are exothermic.

Now, K_A values can be interpreted with one concept fairly well. In general, all the ionic species involved in equation (1) are solvated to various extent. In the present work, it will be necessary to call attention to the solvations of Sr^{2+} and SrNO_3^+ . It has been found that there is a close relationship between the K_A values and the strength of solvation of Sr^{2+} in different solvents; that is, the stronger Sr^{2+} is solvated, the weaker association between Sr^{2+} and NO_3^- becomes in glycerol- H_2O mixtures. From ion solvation free energies and free energies of transfer of metal ion in water and glycerol- H_2O mixtures, it will be certain that the Sr^{2+} solvation free energies in glycerol- H_2O mixtures are a little larger than those in water¹⁰.

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS FOR ASSOCIATION OF $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ IN GLYCEROL- H_2O MIXTURES AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Glycerol %	t °C	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\circ$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
10	25	116.39	5.39	372.50
	30	116.39	5.08	367.35
	35	116.39	4.77	362.41
	40	116.39	4.36	357.91
30	25	90.69	6.57	382.29
	30	90.69	6.36	278.31
	35	90.69	6.12	274.59
	40	90.69	5.89	270.95
50	25	71.26	7.98	212.35
	30	71.26	7.92	209.04
	35	71.26	7.81	205.99
	40	71.26	7.57	203.47

The Sr^{2+} solvation free energies (ΔG°) in glycerol- H_2O mixtures were calculated theoretically using equation of Born¹¹ which adapted by Latimer *et al.*¹². The values of

ΔG° steadily increase in the order : 10% < 30% < 50% glycerol- H_2O having the same trend of K_A values. There is a good linear relationship between ΔG° ($= -RT \ln K_A$) and $\Delta G^\circ_{\text{S}}$. Hence, it is first thought that the solvation energies of ions are a very important factor in controlling ionic association effectively, when the solvation of ions (in glycerol- H_2O mixtures) is weak to some extent, the greater is the association.

If we now consider the anion solvation of NO_3^- from the point of view of anion structure, the nitrate ion is a symmetrical pyramid with a net unit charge. NO_3^- may enter into the soft primary solvation shell of Sr^{2+} in solvent which have a large solvation free energy (a weak solvation), or a part of NO_3^- ions forming ion-pairs with Sr^{2+} ions may be substituted for solvent molecules in the primary solvation shells and the others may be outside the shells.

Experimental

Strontium nitrate (A.R.) was used. Water was double-distilled and then passed through a column containing mixed resin (anion-cation exchangers). Glycerol was purified as described earlier³. Glycerol- H_2O mixtures were prepared by weight. The conductance values of 10% (w/w) glycerol- H_2O were 5.08×10^{-5} , 5.43×10^{-5} , 6.63×10^{-5} and 6.98×10^{-5} s cm⁻¹ at 25, 30, 35 and 40° respectively. The exact concentration of stock solutions was determined by the ion-exchange resin procedure.

The electrical conductance measurements were carried out with a LBR conductivity meter equipped with a cell (LTA 100); the cell constant value was 1.00 cm⁻¹. The measurements were carried out at 25, 30, 35 and 40° in a thermostat ($\pm 0.01^\circ$). The concentrations of measured solutions were in the range 1.5×10^{-4} to 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³.

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